

Towards Using Machine Learning Emulation for Probabilistic Inundation Mapping: Multiple Earthquake Sources and Near-field Effects

Naveen Ragu Ramalingam¹, Erlend Briseid Storrøsten²,
Steven J. Gibbons², Gareth Davies⁴, Stefano Lorito³,
Manuela Volpe³, Fabrizio Romano³, Alice Abbate^{3,5},
Finn Løvholt⁴

¹The University School for Advanced Studies - IUSS Pavia, Pavia, Italy.

²The Norwegian Geotechnical Institute, Oslo, Norway.

³Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Roma, Italy.

⁴Geoscience Australia, Symonston, Australia.

⁵University of Trieste, Trieste, Italy.

Abstract

Machine learning (ML) is emerging as a promising strategy for modelling tsunami inundation at reduced computational cost. We utilise offshore waveforms and local coseismic deformation to predict high-resolution inundation, focusing on the critical aspects of developing and validating an ML emulator that generalises well. Key issues are the training event selection, architecture design, pretraining and training strategy. We utilise an encoder-decoder emulator, trained and tested using an extensive Mediterranean Sea tsunami simulation dataset including near-field events with local deformation for two Eastern Sicily target sites, and achieve good performance for relatively sparse training sets. We demonstrate the potential of ML emulators to accurately model a range of tsunami sources needed for probabilistic tsunami hazard analysis, reducing the computational cost 30-fold. Comparing probabilistic tsunami inundation maps from the complete simulation dataset with those from emulation, we also demonstrate the efficacy of emulators in capturing the spatial distribution and extent of inundation.

Keywords: Machine learning, tsunami inundation, emulator, probabilistic tsunami hazard

1 Introduction

Tsunami inundation is challenging and resource-intensive to model as it involves high resolution numerical simulations most often solving the nonlinear shallow water equations. For probabilistic applications dealing with long-term tsunami hazard or acute alert situations, the effects of the source uncertainty should be addressed by considering a sufficiently large ensembles of scenarios. Thus both adequate time and necessary computational for such simulations can be out of reach [1, 2]. To deal with constraints due to limited computational resources, the ensemble size of the sources has often been restricted based on clustering, statistical sampling, and other reduction techniques, which introduce an additional source of uncertainty [1–6]. When feasible, higher numbers of scenarios can still be considered to reduce this uncertainty, for example using High-Performance Computing (HPC) [7].

Emulators can generate approximate predictions across many scenarios with training on a limited number of simulations. Their design should align with the location, available data and resources and guided by the particular application. Statistical emulators offer fast approximation with error estimates given by a statistical distribution [8–10]. Large tsunami simulation datasets can be used for training the machine learning models (MLMs), for example using neural networks, and in turn be exploited as emulators [11–14]. The focus of MLMs has typically been on the use of emulators for early warning applications, and concentrate on near-field tsunamis for sites proximal to the earthquake source region (e.g. Cascadia [15], Nankai [16], Tohoku [12, 17], Chile [13]).

In previous works [18, 19], we explored the potential and feasibility of such site-specific ML emulators to predict the high-resolution inundation maps using tsunami waveforms from point locations offshore as inputs. In particular, in [18], we considered three subduction zones at different distances from the inundation site, on which an ensemble of 28000 scenarios were initially defined for a site-specific Probabilistic Tsunami Hazard Analysis (PTHA, [7]). We found that our MLM could greatly reduce the computational load of numerically expensive inundation ensemble simulations, using a relatively small training dataset consisting of only a few hundred earthquake scenarios. We also investigated the sensitivity of the predictive performance to MLM features, such as the number of kernels, the latent space, and the loss function.

However, our previous study [18] left some open questions; notably, the MLM was neither trained nor tested with near-field sources that produce permanent uplift or subsidence at the site of interest, and only relatively long-wavelength subduction events were considered. With this in mind, we develop here a more general emulator for PTHA workflows to deal with limited training datasets or resources. Our primary objective is to improve the computational efficiency of inundation predictions while evaluating the source-related uncertainty in a realistic situation.

We present enhancements necessary to consider a larger variety of sources, including crustal earthquakes and near-field events. Local earthquakes can cause significant coastal subsidence or uplift, as also witnessed in the recent 2024 Noto Earthquake [20]. Time-series data of ground displacement from geodetic observations of Global navigation satellite system (GNSS) have been used as MLM inputs for real-time

Fig. 1 Two-stage training approach: (Stage 1) Pre-training three autoencoders to train relevant encoder and decoder layers and (Stage 2) Coupling pre-trained layers of the encoders and decoders and finetuning the connection using interface layers to build the emulator.

forecasting[21]. Analogously, we employ the static local deformation field as an additional input to our emulator. We also enhance the training procedure with pretraining and finetuning, as sketched in Figure 1. Pretraining and finetuning are known to facilitate efficient and stable training and perform transfer learning [22–24]. Pre-trained layers with weights from ML models handling key tsunami variables are used as input and output network layers in the emulator. This is compared with the traditional approach, which begins with randomised weights to directly train the emulator. We demonstrate how implementing these technical improvements can be used to build emulators for PTHA use, and compare the emulation results with those using conventional HPC techniques [7].

Fig. 2 (A) Map of the model region showing the two test sites of Catania and Siracusa. The input gauge locations have a depth of approximately 50 meters, and are marked on the map with following ranges: Catania from 35 to 44, and Siracusa from 53 to 58. (B) the coastal study region in a wider context.

The emulators are developed for two coastal regions of Catania and Siracusa in Eastern Sicily, Italy (Figure 2), exploiting a pre-existing extensive database of inundation simulations previously used for PTHA [7, 25]. Both regions are at risk of tsunami inundation from multiple sources of subduction and crustal earthquakes in the Mediterranean region, including local sources [25, 26].

2 Results

2.1 Tsunami dataset: multiple sources, mechanisms and test sites

We model tsunami inundation with a spatial resolution of 10 m at Catania and Siracusa in eastern Sicily from submarine earthquakes in the Mediterranean Sea: both subduction earthquakes in the Calabrian, Hellenic, and Cyprian arcs and intra-plate crustal earthquakes (see Figure 3 panels A,B). The modelling experiments are supported by a precomputed dataset of 53,550 synthetic events, based on the hazard disaggregation from the NEAMTHM18 Tsunami Hazard Model [26] and summarised in Table A1 and Figure 3(C-G). The tsunami waveforms and local high-resolution inundation are modelled using stochastic heterogeneous slip for earthquake events from three subduction interfaces and uniform slip on rectangular faults for crustal-type events [7, 27, 28]. These simulations were carried out using the Tsunami-HySEA implementation of the non-linear shallow water equations [29] and were executed on Tier0 high-performance computers under the ChEESE project [30].

The characteristics of the earthquake source and how the rupture mechanisms are modelled have a significant impact on the pattern of initial seafloor deformation and

the resulting tsunami [31]. Any tendency of the emulator to overfit on some waveform features would affect the generalisation of the emulator and prediction accuracy. The properties of simulated tsunamis are sensitive to the choices made in rupture modelling: whether a planar or three-dimensional fault surface is used, whether the slip distribution is homogeneous or heterogeneous, and the range of fault-rupture parameters used. Different source features imply different interactions of the ensuing tsunami with the bathymetry and coastal morphology on which it propagates. The representations of different sources have varying complexity, described as background seismicity (BS) for crustal events and predominant seismicity (PS) type for subduction events [26, 28].

The two regions, Catania and Siracusa, are characterised by very different coastal morphology. The Bay of Catania is an open beach with a smooth coastal shelf, resulting in gradual shoaling and inundation over large areas for relatively low amplitude tsunami waves offshore. In contrast, Siracusa is a closed bay with steep slopes onshore and offshore, leading to much greater inundation heights but with less area inundated. The coastline of Siracusa is exposed to inundation both from south and east. Resonance effects [32] may influence the inundation characteristics at different locations within the bay. Local earthquakes affected this region in 1169, 1693, and 1908 [33]. Local onshore deformation can significantly influence the inundation area and depths. The onshore deformation can take the form of uplift or subsidence throughout the coast of interest, or include both uplift and subsidence within the same coastline. Recognising and integrating such variability is crucial for building a robust tsunami source, propagation and inundation database, used for training an emulator that reliably predicts for diverse scenarios and sites.

2.1.1 Selection of the training sets

Our goal is to model inundation on the basis of the offshore waves and local deformation and it is assumed that we can simulate these for the entire set of events at relatively low cost. The MLM needs to be trained on a limited number of full inundation simulations (run at much higher computational cost) and selecting an appropriate subset of events for which the full simulation is performed is crucial. We can select events only on the basis of the source parameters or the simulated offshore time-series. Previous approaches have focused mainly on accounting for the variability across the earthquake magnitude range [12, 13]. Mulia et al [17] used Green’s function summation technique to efficiently generate offshore time-series and analyse the variability of input wave heights to reduce the number of full inundation simulation. A set of training events chosen randomly from a PTHA scenario set would almost certainly be dominated by the (more frequently occurring) lower magnitude events. The selection criteria for a limited training event subset giving adequate representation of all anticipated levels of inundation severity would need to include far more large magnitude events than the proportion determined by the occurrence rates [18]. We of course cannot know, for example, the distribution of flow depths without having first performed the inundation simulations. Sampling strategies for choosing events which best cover the anticipated ranges must therefore depend on proxy variables [3, 4], such as source parameters, local deformation, or offshore wave heights. We test the accuracy of the

Fig. 3 (A) Histogram of the subduction-type (PS or predominant seismicity) earthquake sources in the dataset. The Calabrian (CL), Hellenic (HL), and Cyprian (CY) subduction zones are represented as triangular meshes and the colours represent the number of PS scenarios that have non-zero slip in each triangular segment. (B) Distribution of crustal (BS or background seismicity) earthquake scenarios contributing significantly to the tsunami hazard on Sicily. The sources are represented as Okada-type rectangular slip and the colour represents the number of BS sources with epicenter within the cell displayed. Note that the vast majority of the BS sources are very local to the coastlines of interest. The local sources range from moderate to large while the more distal BS sources are all in the upper-magnitude range. (C) Distribution of earthquake magnitude (M_w) of scenarios for the different categories of earthquake scenarios. The closest subduction earthquakes in the dataset (CL) cover a wide range of magnitudes while the more distal subduction zones (HL and CY) contribute mostly large magnitude earthquakes. (D, E, F, G) Histograms of tsunami metrics as labelled for the Catania and Siracusa test sites in the training set (size 2) and total set of simulations. Note that only the absolute deformation (D) and max. offshore wave height (E) is available for selecting the training set. The inundation area (F) and max. inundation height (G) are results of the inundation calculations and are only known for scenarios for which the full simulation has been performed. The aim is that full simulations will only be performed for scenarios selected as training events on the basis of the deformation and offshore wave heights.

emulator after training them with different numbers of events. This helps to identify an optimal training strategy across the two regions, and understand the trade-offs between dataset size, training approach and predictive performance. We tested four training sets consisting of approximately 1.8%, 3.3%, 7% and 13% of the total number of events, each designed to capture a wide range of event characteristics. Our selection method emphasises the extreme range of the inputs to better capture large and rare events (see section [Sampling procedure](#)). The second training set, with about 3.3% of the total number of events, will be referred to as the Small Training Size (STS). This size was selected as a reasonable number of events that can be simulated during a local tsunami hazard study and is used to evaluate the challenges we may encounter when dealing with limited training datasets. Figure 3(D-G) highlights the class imbalance of events between the basis set given by the overall simulation dataset of 53550 events and the STS training set shown in comparison for the test sites. The ridge and box plots for the different training set sizes and the basis set are depicted in Figures A1 and Figure A2.

2.2 Emulation results

2.2.1 Influence of local deformation as input, the pre-training approach, and training set size

We evaluate whether incorporating the local deformation field as an additional input and the use of pretraining and fine-tuning can improve the predictions. Three model configurations defined in section [Emulator configurations](#) are compared:

1. No pretraining of the encoder and decoder layers, only offshore waveforms are used as input.
2. No pretraining as above; both offshore waveform and local deformation are used as input.
3. With pretraining of the encoder and decoder layers, both offshore waveform and local deformation are used as input.

The model architecture and the learning framework followed in these three configurations are discussed in section [Learning framework](#). The different emulator configurations are trained with the STS training events mentioned above in section [Selection of the training sets](#). When sparse training information is available, we would like to distinguish the impact and benefits of the additional input and pre-training. We quantified the test loss using the MSE loss function calculated on the 25% of the training dataset (~ 400) reserved for model evaluation and parameter setup. The test loss in Figure 4A highlights the performance of different configurations, with the pre-training-based approach converging to a much lower test loss with fewer iterations, especially at the Siracusa site. Pre-training also leads to more stable learning, without large deviations during training iterations (Figure 4). While the results from the loss curve are encouraging they are not definitive due to the small number of events used in this evaluation.

Fig. 4 (A) Comparison of the test loss for the different training approaches using the train size 1: Grey and green lines mark the test loss for approaches without pre-training where all the layers of the emulator are trained together with or without local deformation as an additional input. The proposed approach coupling pre-trained layers and fine-tuning their interface is shown in purple. (B) Scatter plot comparing the distribution test loss given by L2 Error(MSE) for the different magnitude of the events given by L2 Norm, plotted for training approaches with(P) and without(WP) pre-training when using local deformation input for the two test sizes and both the test sites. First row are for the 25% test split from the available training data and the bottom row is for the remaining simulation data used for training. Cumulative MSE for the two test sizes are provided for the two approaches.

We further evaluate the reconstruction error for the two configurations that use the local deformation as input, that is (2) without pre-training and (3) with pre-training. The cumulative MSE Table 3 across test events is calculated by summing the squared errors only at inundation grid locations with depths of at least 20 cm, ensuring the analysis focuses on depths causing significant impacts and avoiding bias in predictions for low-depths. We use two sets of test events for this evaluation, the first with 25% of the STS training data withheld for testing (as used previously), and the second with all remaining events in our simulation database not used in training. A validation set as complete as the one used here is typically not available due to the associated computational cost. It of course enables a better representation of the model’s performance across the large ensemble of events.

Our analysis found that the pretrained emulator has a lower reconstruction error (MSE) on the small test set, but a greater error for the validation set shown in Figure 4B and C. This error difference is linked to the size, variety and distribution of the event magnitudes and characteristics. The second validation set contains considerably more lower to moderate magnitude events. Prediction examples for the different configuration emulators are shown in Figure 5, 6 and 7. The emulator without pre-training better fits on events with local deformation, while the pretrained emulator performs better on events without deformation and events with smaller inundation. These findings underscore the need for a large and diverse dataset for both training and testing.

With increasing training size we expect the emulator predictions to improve. Assessment of the error distribution when training an emulator across different training sizes and configurations can help to refine an optimal training strategy. We investigate the emulator prediction for Catania by comparing the distribution of the error (MSE) relative to the magnitude of inundation ($L2Norm$) for two intermediate sizes, for configurations without and with pretraining as seen in Figure 8. Additional figures corresponding to all the four training set sizes for both the regions and configurations are made available in Figures B3, B4, B5, B6. The (cumulative) MSE value is lower when the emulator is trained without pretraining at training set size 3.3% and marginally at 7%. With the use of pretraining, the error is reduced for small events with a log L2 Norm value of less than -1. The cumulative MSE for the emulator without pretraining are lower for all sizes except for the largest training size 13%. In the Siracusa region, the error distribution aligns with the findings observed for Catania.

When training with sizes 7% and 13%, the emulator with pretraining has a lower cumulative error, highlighting the benefit of pretraining for sites with complex topography like Siracusa and when training with moderate and large training data.

2.3 Predictive accuracy for unseen data

This section tests the emulators trained with the STS set, using model configuration 2 for Catania and configuration 3 for Siracusa. The test set consists of more than 50000 events that were not used during the model training. The prediction examples (Figure 5 for Catania and Figure 7 for Siracusa) provide an overview of the different types of events predicted, events occurring near-field associated with local deformation and those occurring far-field. Figures 6 and 7 also show some adverse examples of events,

Fig. 5 Sample prediction from the test set at Catania. (A) Event without significant local deformation for earthquake from a BS source. (B) Event with local deformation causing significant subsidence at the inundation site from earthquake of BS source. (C) Event without significant local deformation for earthquake from a Hellenic PS source region.

Fig. 6 Prediction of events #50682, #36745 at Catania whose MSE are among the highest ten events. These events are characterised by partial subsidence and uplift occur at the inundation site from local earthquake of BS source. Emulators utilising local deformation field as additional input are able to emulate such events but have significant misfit in the predicted depths.

Fig. 7 Sample prediction from the test set at Siracusa. (A-B) Events with significant local deformation causing subsidence and uplift for earthquakes from local BS source. (C) Event #51052 with partial subsidence and uplift for earthquakes from local BS source is among the events whose MSE is among the highest ten. (D) Event without local deformation for earthquake from Hellenic PS source region.

Fig. 8 Influence of increasing training size on the Catania emulator prediction for the training and basis set using the two learning configurations. The scatter plots show the train-test distribution of log MSE vs. log L2 norm as shown previously in Figure 4B. The rows display the changes with an increase in training size, nearly doubling from 3.3% to 7% while the columns compare results from emulator with and without the pre-training approach.

which the emulator fails to predict well and are among the highest ten reconstruction error (MSE). For these events the deformation interface passes through the inundation location and large parts of the topography are uplifted or subsided.

The Goodness of fit (G) (Table. 3) is used as a performance measure of the similarity of the simulation and emulation prediction ranging between 0-1 with value to close to 0 identical. The overview of the G for the complete test set is shown in Figure 9A. The model predictions are satisfactory across the events with inundation above a certain threshold of 5000 pixels (out of the total 579439 prediction locations). The events with poor prediction, where G is greater than 0.3 are those with earthquake magnitudes below Mw 8, offshore wave heights less than 30 cm, and a small number of far-field events from the Cyprus source.

2.3.1 Sensitivity to earthquake origin, inundation locations and depths

Fig. 9 (A) Prediction performance across different earthquake and tsunami parameters. (B) This figure compares the prediction performance for the location of earthquake origin in the training and test set. The top row displays all events from the training set, where the performance is very good ranging with the G typically below 0.1. The second row highlights all test events with at poor predictions by filtering events with G greater than 0.3. We exclude events associated with minor flooding, by removing those with fewer than 5,000 inundated pixels from a total of 579,439 locations potentially affecting Catania. This map displays the small set of location related to local BS type earthquake origins and a few Calabrian Arc PS events which are poorly predicted.

To assess whether the emulator performance is sensitive to the location of the earthquake origin, we plot the G values for the 444 unique locations in the training set with significant inundation exceeding 5,000 pixels (Figure 9B). The same analysis for the test set highlights a small group of 115 events with 37 origin locations of local BS type (34), Calabrian Arc (1) and Hellenic Arc (2) of PS type where the prediction from the emulator is not accurate, with G greater than 0.3, and confirms that the emulator does not overfit to the earthquake origins it was trained on and generalises well for our large test set. Section [Feasibility for PTHA use](#) discusses the physical characteristics

Fig. 10 (A) Compares the prediction performance with R^2 at the inundation grids from [18], Current work for test with PS events only and the complete test set. (B) Heat map histogram of the R^2 for the all the test events and the flood occurrence in the training events.

of these events in more details and the sensitivity of emulator performance to them using a correlation analysis.

Understanding the reliability of inundation emulation at different locations is crucial, given imbalanced training information. We visually compare the change in the model performance from Storrøsten et al. [18] across the inundation locations using R^2 for a similar test set consisting of the only PS types subduction events and the full test set of the current work as shown in Figure 10 A. There is marked difference in the southern region where values reduced from band above 0.8 to that between 0.6 to 0.8. When including BS type events into the evaluation for the complete test set the score shows much better performance. The heat map in Figure 10 B shows the significant improvements in the R^2 score when at least 30, 100 and 200 instances of inundation information is available for the grids during training. We provide a more comprehensive analysis of the prediction quality by using various evaluation metrics and a subset of test events of a particular types across all the prediction locations and at specific control points in supplement section [Location analysis](#).

2.4 Feasibility for PTHA use

In the previous sections we assessed the suitability of the ML emulator by evaluating its reconstruction capability for individual events from a large tsunami simulation dataset generated for a site-specific PTHA. This helped identifying the type of events and locations where further consideration is needed in their construction and use. To look at the results over the whole ensemble altogether, we generate probability of exceedance maps for various depth thresholds using both simulation and emulation results (11). The hazard zonation is consistent between both methods, indicating that the general behaviour of the system is well captured. However, regions with exceedance probabilities below 10^{-6} show some underestimation, evident in the yellow zones outlined in blue on maps for depths exceeding 3 m and 5 m. This deviation suggests that

Fig. 11 Comparison of the probabilistic maps of tsunami inundation for Catania between (A) the complete inundation simulation for 53,550 events with Tsunami-Hysea and (B) those generated with the emulation results described in section [Predictive accuracy for unseen data](#). The hazard exceedance zones are defined by the annual probability of exceeding inundation depths of 20 cm, 1 m, 3 m, and 5 m. For easier comparison, the hazard zones are marked with regions exceeding 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} , and 10^{-7} from panel A overlaid on panel B with light blue, white, black, and blue lines. The hazard zones show consistent patterns; however, areas with exceedance probabilities below 10^{-6} are depicted in yellow and light yellow, and their comparison indicates an underestimation by the emulator.

while the emulator effectively reproduces the overall trends, it could be further refined to enhance its accuracy in predicting low-probability events. Nonetheless, for a better characterisation of the consistency between the simulation and emulation-based PTHA, and to judge the impact of these deviations for practical applications, these deviations should be compared with the epistemic uncertainty of the model, which will be addressed in a future study.

Table 1 Overview of machine learning training time, MSE , and weighted MSE in reconstructing the inundation for all events in the PTHA event set of 53,550 for Catania and Siracusa using an emulator trained with different training set sizes. The weighted MSE is calculated by multiplying the mean probability of occurrence of each event with its respective MSE . The percentage variation in error with increasing training size between consecutive sets is shown in parentheses.

Region	Model Type	Training Set (%)	Training Time (min)	MSE (% Change)	Weighted MSE (% Change)
Catania	No	1.8%	82	667.32	1.41e-05
		3.3%	146	508.86 (23.75%)	1.30e-05 (7.54%)
		7%	284	425.03 (16.47%)	1.07e-05 (17.77%)
		13%	333	357.04 (15.997%)	9.02e-06 (15.95%)
	Pretraining	1.8%	92.5	764.29	1.68e-05
		3.3%	104.5	607.30 (20.54%)	1.24e-05 (26.47%)
		7%	155	399.73 (34.18%)	9.05e-06 (27.05%)
		13%	220	310.31 (22.37%)	6.22e-06 (31.26%)
Siracusa	No	1.8%	45	759.89	1.02e-05
		3.3%	51	518.73 (31.74%)	8.46e-06 (17.07%)
		7%	143	543.15 (-4.71%)	6.54e-06 (22.68%)
		13%	143	397.56 (26.80%)	5.28e-06 (19.25%)
	Pretraining	1.8%	91.25	713.13	1.03e-05
		3.3%	99	522.75 (26.70%)	6.77e-06 (34.71%)
		7%	121	344.01 (34.19%)	4.64e-06 (31.51%)
		13%	174	266.75 (22.46%)	3.61e-06 (22.14%)

Table 2 Overview of run times for numerical simulation using Tsunami-Hysea and emulation accounting for the ML training and prediction times for generating PTHA data for 53,550 events in Catania and Siracusa. Run times are measured for Tsunami-Hysea simulation and ML training run on a single NVIDIA A100 GPU while ML prediction on a single core of an 2.45 GHz AMD EPYC 7763 CPU.

Region	Method	# Events	Run Time (min)
Catania+ Siracusa	Simulation(1 Event)	1	25
	Simulation(Training Data)	3.3%	44325
	Simulation(Brute Force)	100%	1338750
Catania	Emulation	100%	24
Siracusa	Emulation	100%	13
Total Emulation Time (Data Generation + Training + Prediction)			44,559 mins
Overall Gain from Emulation with 3.3% Training Data			30 x

Increasing the training size leads to marked improvements in model prediction, indicated by the decreasing MSE seen in Table 1. For Catania, the MSE error decreased progressively from 667.32 to 357.04, indicating a reduction of 46.50% across the training sizes from 1.8% to 13% without pretraining. With pretraining, the reduction was even more substantial, reaching a lower MSE error from 764.29 to 310.31, a reduction of 59.38%. For Siracusa, the MSE error decreased from 759.89 to 397.56 without pretraining, a reduction of 47.70%, and from 713.13 to 266.75 with pretraining reducing by 62.59%. The percentage change in MSE between consecutive training sizes also shows that the most significant improvements occur when increasing from smaller to moderately larger training sizes between 1.8% to 7%. Contrary to initial expectation that the impact of the pretraining would be beneficial with smallest training sizes and information, our experiments suggests that pretraining helps providing a balanced and stable training for moderate sizes. The weighted MSE in all cases except the smallest training size had lower error for emulators with pretraining. This underscores that along with architecture, amount of training information and its quality, the training approach can also influence development of accurate emulators.

With limited training information and focus on a wide range of events types and magnitude, events greater than 5000 pixels inundated are well predicted and could supplement available simulation for a larger ensemble inundation PTHA. We plotted the distribution of G for the events against the different tsunami parameters, with values above 0.3 considered poorly predicted and below 0.3 as well predicted. This was done to verify if emulator generalises well and identify if sensitive to certain physical characteristics of the event as shown in Figure 12. We also calculated the correlation coefficient(r) with for the Logit value of G using these two sets of events marked as good and bad for each tsunami parameter. For Catania Figure 9B mapped the location of these events with G greater than 0.3, which are mainly the local BS source events with local deformation mechanism. There is a high count of events with mixed deformation and subsiding events in the bad portion, with the rof 0.3 for the peak deformation showing some association with poor prediction. For Siracusa, a larger number of events with inundation smaller than 5000 pixels are removed, leaving 359 events that the emulator predicts poorly with G values higher than 0.3. Unlike Catania, here the poor model performance can not be correlated to a specific kind of events. Due to the complexity in the inundation, a focus on smaller regions using a modular, model of local models approach could be useful.

3 Discussion

The design of our tsunami inundation emulator presents significant enhancements for application in PTHA hazard aggregation: applicability to diverse tsunamigenic earthquake sources (including local seismicity), explicit use of co-seismic deformation as model input, and an alternative ML workflow (with pretraining of the model components). The pretraining technique demonstrably enhances the stability and efficiency of training with limited data. Pretraining speeds up training by initialising models layers with targeted parameters exploiting the different amount of available data for the inputs and outputs. It improves predictions for the complex topography, smaller

Fig. 12 Correlation of the prediction quality given by the G values shown for different tsunami physical parameter at (A) Catania and (B) Siracusa.

events, and succeeds in amplifying/reducing the inundation because of subsidence/uplift, but lacks the flexibility needed to emulate complex events featuring both uplift and subsidence at different places within the calculation domain. For such events, emulators which directly train all layers, by initialising them from scratch perform better than the pretrained ones.

Future steps in this direction could involve augmenting the datasets used to train the onshore autoencoder, potentially from other domains or synthetic datasets. This

could help to cover characteristics of the rarer scenarios and maximise the benefits of pre-training the decoder with disproportionate datasets, for more accurate predictions and greater generalisation of the emulator across broader scenario ranges.

Emulator generalisation depends on careful selection of training events to reduce bias while encouraging variability needed for PTHA. The emulator is comprehensive in its design, taking multiple data sources as input and accounting for near-field effects, making it a robust tool for tsunami inundation modelling considering diverse inundation conditions. We evaluated the performance of our emulator using an extensive PTHA simulation dataset for two test sites with very different coastal morphologies. One of the key learning from our training experiments is that the model scale, that is the number of locations predicted, must be configured to the characteristics of the location. Although smaller in the number of prediction locations, the model for the Siracusa domain could be split into two smaller sections focusing on the southern and eastern inundation regions separately. This approach would reduce the complexity introduced by its coastal setting. The prediction obtained with the emulator should then be compared with the uncertainty span of the PTHA estimates, like for statistical sampling reduction approaches [2], ideally with uncertainty and error quantification contextual to the emulation [19, 34]. Further analysis of the MLM performance for PTHA applications is left for future work.

Apart from managing the complexity of the prediction site, we may use a training set of optimal size and distribution. Gains in performance diminish beyond a certain size which depend on several factors, including input variability, output variability, range and number of prediction locations. Understanding this cost of training is essential for optimising prediction skill and associated costs in different environments, requiring more investigation on the influence of selection and sampling schemes while training dataset creation. This study found a 30x saving in the computational cost when replacing the inundation predictions using emulators trained with a modest 3.3% of the event ensemble for PTHA, as it can be seen by comparing run times between numerical simulation and emulation in Table 2.

In the current form, we recognise the importance of narrowing the focus of the emulator on the intermediate range of tsunami events. A limited number of extreme and small-scale events should perhaps be fully simulated, while the emulator can effectively function as a replacement for intermediate events where a much higher number of simulations are needed. However, defining this intermediate range poses a challenge and necessitates a small set of initial simulations to base a balanced representation. Nonetheless, even for simulation-based PTHA, the uncertainties are larger in the right tail; furthermore a thorough uncertainty quantification from other sources of epistemic and aleatory uncertainty like the topo-bathymetric dataset, failure of defences, impact of tides, and relative sea level rise are also important to consider [9, 35, 36] and can be incorporated in such a workflow in the future.

Our work lays the foundation for a powerful tool for modelling tsunami inundation and it is the first example, to the best of our knowledge, in which an emulator of this kind is used for a full site-specific PTHA. With refinements, the emulator can become more adaptable and efficient, providing crucial insights for tsunami preparedness and risk management.

4 Methods

4.1 Selection and size of training data

Training dataset size and selection procedure affect emulator training quality and prediction skill. The size of the training data set is typically limited by the computational budget available to generate them [7, 37] or by the reuse of existing datasets available [15, 16, 38]. To consider the impact of multiple sources and inundation mechanisms, we refine our selection based on (a) the maximum absolute deformation across the onshore inundation grids, (b) the maximum amplitude offshore on a representative gauge, and (c) the location of the earthquake discussed in more detail in the following section [Sampling procedure](#). The number of events required, especially to account for variability in the inundation across the possible location affected, is typically sensitive to the study site’s topography, coastal and continental shelf/slope characteristics, along with the tsunami sources affecting such a region. We evaluated this requirement by testing the different components and configurations of the model in different training sizes, as noted in [Table C3](#).

We picked the training data, with the following following strategy :

1. We select training sets consisting of approximately 1.8%,3.3%,7% and 13% of the overall 53550 events simulation set for Catania and and Siracusa to train the respective onshore autoencoders.
2. We used the largest selection of 13% events from the step 1, to also train the offshore waveform autoencoders for the regions.
3. All events in the database with significant deformation of at least 10 cm on the onshore grids are selected to train the deformation autoencoder; this amounts to 7929 and 9186 events for Catania and Siracusa, respectively.
4. We also use the different training sets from step 1, for training the three emulators of different configurations.

4.1.1 Sampling procedure

To ensure sufficient variability in our tsunami dataset, we adopt a stratified sampling approach, focusing on several key factors: source type (BS and PS), source location, local deformation, with emphasis on the extreme events (high-magnitude and low-likelihood events). We divide the data into subsets: events with and without local deformation, and further into subduction type (PS) and crustal type (BS). The sampling procedure is described by the following steps:

1. **Deformation split** Divide events into Deformation Events (events causing > 10 cm of absolute deformation on land grids) and Non-Deformation Events (events causing < 10 cm deformation).
2. **Preserve train and test sets**, for both categories (Deformation and Non-Deformation), split the events into two halves for training and testing.
3. **Percentile based sampling for deformation events**
 - (a) Separate Deformation Events into: **Group A**: Events below the 90th percentile of maximum onshore deformation. **Group B**: Events above the 90th percentile of maximum onshore deformation.

- (b) Sample events from each of the two groups using 10 bins, picking n events per bin.
 - (c) Sample events like Step 3(a) and(b) based on maximum offshore wave height as sampling parameter.
4. **Percentile based sampling for non-deformation events**
- (a) For BS Events, sample events like Step 3(a) and (b) based on maximum offshore wave height as sampling.
 - (b) For PS Events, sample events like Step 3(a) and (b) based on maximum offshore wave height as sampling parameters, but picking $3n$ events per bin (3 times more PS events than BS events).
5. **Combine events** selected through steps 3 and 4 and remove any duplicates.

To select the four increasing training set sizes, $n = 9, 18, 42$ and 100 was used. Upon removing the duplicate events we sampled 892, 1658, 3454 and 7071 events for Catania and 961, 1773, 3669 and 6941 events for Siracusa. This approach captures the diversity of events, providing a robust and varied training set for our machine learning models. Table C2 list the training set sizes used for different MLM components.

4.2 Learning framework

4.2.1 Data structure

Beyond training set sizes, other factors can significantly affect the complexity and training of the machine learning emulator. These include the specification of input and output data, what they describe, and the level of detail. Key considerations are:

- **Input Location and Quantity:** The challenge of modelling varies according to where and how many input points are considered. For instance, inputs from deep ocean sensors (like S-net sensors) differ in complexity from those at offshore points with 50-100m depth or at low resolution onshore.
- **Temporal Information:** The amount of time information available (e.g. 20-30 minutes of information when using sensors versus 4-6 hours when using a modelled approximation as input) can influence the sufficiency of data about the entire event.
- **Additional Factors:** In our work, we include the local earthquake deformation that affects inundation. However, other conditions, such as tides and local sea level rise, can also be considered in such emulation frameworks.
- **Prediction Locations:** We need to predefine the prediction locations, this can range from a single site of importance to multiple locations. The number of locations together with complexity based on local topography impacts the model parameter optimisation given limited training data.

We process waveforms consisting of 480 data points (4 hour simulation time with 30 second sampling) from the 9 gauge sites closest to Catania and the 5 closest to Siracusa for the respective inundation predictions. The predictions are made on a predefined subset of locations of the finest resolution grids, determined from the flood envelope using the inundation information available from the training set. This results in 579439 and 224124 prediction locations for Catania and Siracusa. To account for the local deformation field, we use the initial displacement available on the 10m grids with

dimensions 911x2222 for Catania and 948x1300 for Siracusa. Table C3 for a summary on the data structure and dimension of the inputs and outputs.

4.2.2 Model architecture

The model architecture for our tsunami inundation emulator incorporates several components and techniques to effectively capture and predict complex inundation patterns. We describe the two main architectures employed in this study, Autoencoder(AE) and Encoder-Decoder(ED). AEs are neural networks designed to learn an efficient and reduced representation of input data by training to reconstruct the input [39]. Our approach uses three distinct AEs to handle three different parameters of the tsunami data:

- AE for tsunami waveforms (AE-Offshore)
- AE for local deformation fields (AE-Deform)
- AE for maximum inundation depth (AE-Onshore)

The emulator model is based on an ED architecture. Encoders compress the input data into a latent space representation, while decoders reconstruct the output data from this compressed form. This architecture allows the model to learn complex mappings between inputs and outputs, crucial for accurate inundation predictions. We use convolutional neural network (CNN) layers [40] for the encoding layers of the emulator based on two pretrained models, AE-Offshore and AE-Deform. These CNN layers are particularly effective for handling spatial and temporal patterns in the tsunami waveforms and deformation fields. The CNNs extract hierarchical features, reducing the dimensionality of the data, while preserving important information that is mapped to the latent space (LS).

The AE-Onshore, also utilised as the decoder in our emulator, features a two-part structure composed of fully connected layers. The first part includes multiple local encoders and decoders that independently process 64 different segments of the input inundation depth map, effectively splitting it into smaller sections. This segmentation [41] helps to limit the input and output dimensions, allowing the model to focus on the precise reconstruction of smaller regions and features. The second part consists of a global encoder and decoder, which processes the concatenated representations from the local encoders and decoders, capturing the broader patterns of inundation. The AE-Onshore architecture, with its ability to split, encode, and decode multiple parts, is particularly beneficial for providing attention to spatial patterns of the inundation map. By enabling specialised reconstruction pathways for each region, the split network reduces the number of parameters and enhances the overall accuracy and efficiency of the emulator. Figure 13 provides a detailed representation of the emulator architecture.

The LS serves as a lower-dimensional representation of the AE inputs and captures essential features of the tsunami waveforms, deformation, or inundation. This compact representation is crucial for the subsequent fine-tuning after coupling stage, forming the final coupled emulator as discussed in section Training procedure.

Several hyperparameters were configured based on the initial results during the pretraining procedure and our previous models [18, 19]. These include the number

Fig. 13 Model architecture of the encoder-decoder emulator presented for the Catania implementation. The flow of data is represented by the initial inputs in the form of waveforms at 9 offshore gauges and the local deformation field that pass through convolutional layers which encode and concatenate them into a combined latent space. This is decoded through linear layers of the global and local decoder, to split them into segments focusing on inundation prediction for smaller regions of Catania.

of channels in for the convolutional and fully connected layers of the encoders and decoder layers, size of latent space, no of inundation segments, train-test split size. Other hyperparameters like batch size, maximum training epochs, learning rate and loss function were adjusted during training iterations. We balance batch size [42] to ensure event variability for each batch given the hardware memory constraints, which typically depends on the input and output variables size. Different loss function are used to training based on the tsunami parameter predicted by the model as discussed in section [Loss function](#). To prevent overfitting and improve generalisation, we employ regularisation techniques such as dropout [43] of 0.1 after the encoding and 0.5 inter-face layers, where a portion of neurons are randomly dropped during training. Early stopping is applied, which halts training when performance on the validation set ceases to improve. The initial learning rate was an important hyper parameter, which sets the step size during for parameter change during training iteration. Adam optimiser [44] is used for adaptive learning rate adjustments during training. The summary of the hyperparameter settings for the different models are made available in [Table C3](#).

4.2.3 Loss function

Two loss functions were employed for different model training steps. The Mean Square Error (MSE) and a Custom Loss Function (CLF), which combines the Mean Cubic Error (MCE) and the Mean Square Error (MSE). These are defined by the following expressions:

$$\text{CLF} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|^3 + 0.5 \cdot \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|^2 \quad (2)$$

where, y_i represents the actual target value, \hat{y}_i represents the predicted value, and n is the number of samples.

The CLF was utilised for training the offshore and onshore autoencoders. This loss function heavily penalises mismatches in peaks or sharp features and higher sensitivity in outliers. The higher penalty for prediction in large values makes CLF suitable when modelling high-frequency and peak values in waveforms and small local inundation features. These loss functions may cause poorer fit for small events and training instability due to outliers, depending on batch or dataset quality.. For the deformation autoencoder and the final fine-tuning of the emulator of different configurations(1-3), the MSE loss function was used. MSE also emphasises the larger prediction errors over the smaller ones while maintaining stability in training. The combination of these loss functions at different stages allows for a balanced approach to model training, addressing the need to minimise overall errors, and significant deviations for certain important features while ensuring robustness and stability in training procedure.

4.2.4 Training procedure

We utilise two different techniques for training our emulators models: traditional direct training and a multi-step approach involving pre-training, coupling, and fine-tuning [45]. These approaches are applied across various configurations to develop robust autoencoders and the final encoder-decoder emulator models.

The training principle behind building an encoder-decoder is to minimise the reconstruction error between the input and the output of the decoder network using back propagation method and a the loss function. When such models are trained to reconstruct the inputs as their outputs, they are called autoencoders.

In the traditional direct training, parameters of the different model layers are initialised with random weights and trained from scratch. This method is straight forward but may require extensive training data and computational resources to achieve satisfactory performance. We apply this approach for training the autoencoders and the emulator models of configurations 1 and 2. We adopt an approach consisting of pre-training, coupling and fine-tuning for building the emulator model of configuration 3.

In the pretraining approach, the three autoencoders are trained on different dataset sizes listed in Table C2 using a traditional direct training. Here the parameters from

the training epoch having the least reconstruction error for the test set are selected as weights for the pretrained AEs when early stopping is triggered. In the coupling step, parts of these autoencoders model are used with their pretrained parameter weights as fixed i.e. they are not updated during subsequent finetuning stage. The CNN offshore encoder, CNN deformation encoder are used as the input layers with their latent space concatenated and the onshore decoder as the output layers. The input and output latent spaces are connected via fully connected (interface) layer to build an integrated encoder-decoder emulator. In the finetuning stage, we only train the parameters of the interface layers, the fully connected layers with linking the latent space of the pretrained encoders and decoders, and the final uninitialised layer of the onshore decoder, leaving the remaining layers and parameters untouched as illustrated in 13. This helps realign the input latent representation as required for the output decoder.

By unlinking the training of the other components from the onshore decoder, we are not limited by the limited computational budget resulting small less inundation data for training. Thus the offshore and deformation encoders can be trained with larger training information in pretraining and be thoroughly validated before coupling. The pretraining phase assists to refine the model architecture, design the encoder and decoder layers more intuitively, enhance the explainability of the layers and provides an understanding of the data flows during prediction. Thus, pretraining ensures robust feature extraction, while coupling and fine-tuning integrates these features for accurate prediction of tsunami inundation.

4.3 Emulator configurations

Using a combination of inputs and training techniques we evaluate three different emulator configuration in this study. In configuration 1 without pretraining, the tsunami waveform data is used as the only input, utilising a direct training method from random initialisation of the parameter weights. Configuration 2 expands upon this by incorporating both tsunami waveform and deformation data as inputs, still employing the direct training method from random initialisation.

Finally, Configuration 3 adopts a pretrain, couple and fine-tune approach, utilising both tsunami waveform and deformation data as input. We follow training the procedure discussed in the previous section [Training procedure](#). The Configurations 1 and 2 offer straightforward applications, while Configuration 3 can help stable training for complex prediction tasks like in the case of Siracusa test site. It also offers the possibility to integrate multiple input and output data sources adhoc. We should note that while pretrained weight are not used in the configuration 1 and 2, the model architecture and relevant hyperparameters were set based on the results pretraining stage.

4.4 Evaluation

The methodology used to evaluate the performance of the final tsunami inundation emulators and their components involved testing several criterias using evaluation metrics with formulation listed in Table 3. These include the $L2norm$ for measuring the event magnitude that accounts for both the area and depths of inundation, MSE

Table 3 Summary of Evaluation Metrics and Formulas

Metric	Formula	Focus
$L2Norm$	$\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$	Magnitude of event
MSE	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$	Prediction Error
Coefficient of Determination (R^2)	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$	Strength of the model
Goodness of Fit (G)	$1 - \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i \hat{y}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{y}_i^2}$	General Performance
Correlation Coefficient (r)	$\frac{n \sum (xy) - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$	Linear Relationship
False Positive Rate (FP)	$\frac{FP+TN}{FN}$	Wrong Prediction
False Negative Rate (FN)	$\frac{FN+TP}{FP}$	Wrong Prediction
True Positive Rate (TP)	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$	Correct Prediction
True Negative Rate (TN)	$\frac{TN}{TN+FP}$	Correct Prediction

for prediction error, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for correlation or dependence, goodness of fit (G) for general performance, the correlation coefficient (r) for linear relationships and use of confusion matrix scores for evaluating the binary classification of flooded or not.

Initially, the performance of the autoencoders was assessed by calculating the reconstruction error on a 25% test portion of the training dataset using metrics such as R^2 , cumulative MSE and G for the test set and individual events. The formulation of G is not sensitive to the value of the inundation depth or number of grids inundated. This analysis helped identify features and event types with poor predictions, leading to iterative improvements in model architecture, hyperparameters, loss functions, and other training attributes.

Upon developing the autoencoders, the final emulator models were tested on all the remaining events of the 53550 event database predictions using predictions at inundation grids exceeding 20 cm, using the same metrics (G , R^2 , MSE). Here the formulas are used both for location wise and scenario wise evaluation. Summation is accordingly taken over a set of scenarios or pixel locations. Additionally, the misfit at control points was evaluated by analysing the distribution of the misfit and the confusion matrix, to classify if the inundation is above or below 20cm with a score for false positives and negatives.

Finally, to measure prediction error for PTHA use, we calculated the MSE by removing events where less than 5000 pixels are inundated. This helped quantify the emulator's improvement with increase training size and different configurations tested. We further identified the relationship of the physical characteristics of the event with the G , this was done by calculating the correlation coefficient(r) of the physical parameters for the logit transformation of G . These metrics provided a comprehensive evaluation of the emulator's performance across different dimensions, ensuring a thorough understanding of its strengths and areas for improvement.

Supplementary information. Additional figures and tables are provided in the Appendix section.

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Author contribution. All authors contributed to the conceptualisation, investigation, and preparation of the manuscript. MV and SJ conducted the numerical simulation and generated the tsunami dataset used for model training and testing. NRR and EB designed the ML emulator. NRR implemented and performed the machine learning training, testing, experiments, prepared the original draft of the manuscript. SL,GD,EB,FL were responsible for technical supervision.

Data availability. The training code, data, and ML emulator are provided as open resources to the community, to enable benchmarking, comparison, and further development, available for preview in the Zenodo repository via the link <https://tinyurl.com/zenodo-ptha-emulator>.

Code availability. Pytorch was used as the machine learning framework within Python, additional analyses were executed through custom Python scripts, and map visualisations were generated using the Pygmt package. The codebase used in this research and the preparation of the manuscript is accessible through this repository https://github.com/naveenragur/ML4SicilyTsunami/tree/ptha_emulators.

Competing interests. All authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Appendix A Simulation and Training Dataset

Fig. A1 Comparison of the Tsunami statistics for the selections of the training set of different sizes at Catania and the simulation dataset as the basis set

Fig. A2 Comparison of the Tsunami statistics for the selections of the training set of different sizes at Siracusa and the simulation dataset as the basis set

Table A1 Tsunami Simulation Database: Earthquake Event Parameters Across Different Sources

Source	Number of events	Mag(Mw)	Lat	Lon	Depth	Dip	Rake	Strike
Crustal(BS)	25041	6-8.09	31.76-40.30	14.14-32-23	1-22.09	10-90	0-270	22.5-337.5
Calabrian(PS)	5396	6.5-8.61	36.56-38.93	15.47-18.63				
Hellenic(PS)	23086	6.8-9.02	33.62-37.99	19.45-26.79				
Cyprus(PS)	27	7.54-8.5	34.59-35.8	30.71-32.91				

Appendix B Detailed Results

B.1 Sensitivity to training size and training approach

Fig. B3 Quality of prediction at different training sizes for Catania for the training and basis set without pre-training.

Fig. B4 Quality of prediction at different training sizes for Catania for the training and basis set with pre-training.

Fig. B5 Quality of prediction at different training sizes for Siracusa for the training and basis set without pre-training.

Fig. B6 Quality of prediction at different training sizes for Siracusa for the training and basis set with pre-training.

B.2 Prediction performance at Siracusa

Fig. B7 (A) Prediction performance across different earthquake and tsunami parameters for Siracusa. (B) Influence of train event locations to poor performance, only events greater than 10 cm in the offshore gauge are shown, small inundation events less than 5000 pixels are also removed to check events not well simulated.

B.3 Location analysis

To evaluate the predicted maximum inundation depths, we apply different metrics described in Table 3 to all locations across the test set events. Figure B8 displays the frequency of flooding in the training set. Areas with frequent flooding provide more training information for the emulator, while regions with infrequent or no flooding offer less information. This imbalance affects the emulator’s ability to accurately predict inundation in less frequently flooded areas, as seen in the R^2 and G map plots in Figure B8. The prediction starts to deteriorate when less than 100 events flood the inundation grids and is unusable for events less than 10 events understood from the poor R^2 and G values at these locations. Additionally the histogram values of Figure 10 B and Figure B12 B show that for locations with frequency of inundation less than 30 in the training set having the R^2 are below 0.6 and G greater than 0.3. This evaluation shows that sites flooded rarely and with less information in training have poorer predictions in the test events and within subsets of test events sourced from different mechanisms, (a) BS, (b) PS, (c) events causing local deformation above 10 cm onshore, and (d) events unaffected by local deformation.

Fig. B8 Location based performance evaluation for Catania. Top row looks at the different evaluation metric at the inundation grids using MSE, R^2 and G . For comparison we provide the frequency of flooding at the grids in the training dataset ranging between less than 10, between 10 to 100 and greater than 100. Bottom row displays the goodness of fit (G) for each location calculated using BS events, PS events, events with local deformations and events without local deformations.

Fig. B9 Location based performance evaluation for Siracusa. Same as B8 with top row looks at the different evaluation metric at the inundation grids. Bottom row evaluates performance within a type of event using G.

When using the mean squared error (MSE) at grid location, considering test events with flood depth of at least 10 cm. The MSE scales with the depth and number of events, we found that nearshore areas with well-defined training information have low error - typically less than 0.4 m^2 . At intermediate locations error values increase due to the scaling effect of poor depth prediction and no of observation. Finally tending to zero near the inland edge, as only a few flooding events occur with small predicted and true depths. It is essential to recognise that MSE is also used as the training loss function, is likely to perform poorly in areas with a low frequency of flooding within the training dataset. Similarly, R^2 can yield unreliable results for evaluation at locations with limited test events, influenced by mean values. Figure B10 and B11 illustrates the misfit in the inundation depth ranges within 1m (between 5 and 95 percentile) at control points positioned at random locations within the region with at least 100 flood occurrences, as shown in Figure B8 and Figure B9. An analysis of the confusion matrix for classifying inundation with at least 20 cm or not found false negatives at locations with limited training information, indicating a general tendency to under predict depth.

Fig. B10 Misfit at control points for Catania shown in B8

Fig. B11 Misfit at control points for Siracusa shown in B9

B.4 PTHA Inundation Maps

We also analysed how the PTHA hazard zones for Catania, where the probabilities of 1-meter inundation depth exceed varies with the accuracy of machine learning (ML) predictions for G values at the location. The spatial comparison is shown in Figure B12 with the different inundation zones defined by the annual probability of exceedance $1e-6, 1e-5, 1e-4$ for 1m of inundation. The heat map of location-specific accuracy metrics further illustrates that the model performs effectively when 30-100 training events inundate the prediction location, as noted before. Similar to the comparison of Figure 11 we compare probabilistic inundation maps generated using simulation and emulation results for two subset of event types, with and without local deformation Figure B13 and Figure B14 .

Fig. B12 (A) Shows the comparison of prediction performance using G at the inundation grids for all test events. The hazard zone delineated with the probability of exceeding 1m with thresholds $10^{-4}, 10^{-5}, 10^{-6}$, and 10^{-7} from Figure 11A is superimposed. (B) Heat map histogram of the G calculated using all test events and the occurrence of flooding in the training events at prediction location as shown in Figure B8

Fig. B13 Comparison of the probabilistic maps of tsunami inundation for events with local deformation at Catania between (A) using simulation with Tsunami-Hysea and (B) those generated with the emulation results. The hazard exceedance zones are defined by the annual probability of exceeding inundation depths of 20 cm, 1 m, 3 m, and 5 m. For easier comparison, the hazard zones are marked with regions exceeding 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} , and 10^{-7} from panel A overlaid on panel B with light blue, white, black, and blue lines. The hazard zones show consistent patterns; however, areas with exceedance probabilities below 10^{-6} are depicted in yellow and light yellow, and their comparison indicates an underestimation by the emulator.

Fig. B14 Comparison of the probabilistic maps of tsunami inundation for events without local deformation at Catania between (A) using simulation with Tsunami-Hysea and (B) those generated with the emulation results. The hazard exceedance zones are defined by the annual probability of exceeding inundation depths of 20 cm, 1 m, 3 m, and 5 m. For easier comparison, the hazard zones are marked with regions exceeding 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , 10^{-6} , and 10^{-7} from panel A overlaid on panel B with light blue, white, black, and blue lines. The hazard zones show consistent patterns; however, areas with exceedance probabilities below 10^{-6} are depicted in yellow and light yellow, and their comparison indicates an underestimation by the emulator.

Appendix C Methods

Table C2 A summary of regions, model names, model types, and their corresponding training sizes.

Region	Model Name	Model Type	Training Sizes
CT	CT-AE-Offshore	AE Offshore	[7071]
	CT-AE-Deform	AE Deformation	[7929]
	CT-AE-Onshore	AE Onshore	[892, 1658, 3454, 7071]
	CT-ED-Emul1	ED Emulator (Config 1)	[892, 1658, 3454, 7071]
	CT-ED-Emul2	ED Emulator (Config 2)	[892, 1658, 3454, 7071]
SR	CT-ED-Emul3	ED Emulator (Config 3)	[892, 1658, 3454, 7071]
	SR-AE-Offshore	AE Offshore	[6941]
	SR-AE-Deform	AE Deformation	[9186]
	SR-AE-Onshore	AE Onshore	[961, 1773, 3669, 6941]
	SR-ED-Emul1	ED Emulator (Config 1)	[961, 1773, 3669, 6941]
	SR-ED-Emul2	ED Emulator (Config 2)	[961, 1773, 3669, 6941]
	SR-ED-Emul3	ED Emulator (Config 3)	[961, 1773, 3669, 6941]

Table C3 An overview of various models utilised in the study along with their corresponding input and output dimensions, latent sizes, learning rates (LR), batch sizes, loss functions, and maximum epochs.

Region	Model Name	Input Dim	Output Dim	Latent Size	LR	Batch Size	Loss Function	Max Epoch
CT	CT-AE-Offshore	[9x480]	[9x480]	64	0.0035	300	MCE	600
	CT-AE-Deform	[912x2224]	[912x2224]	64	0.0025	100	MSE	300
	CT-AE-Onshore	[579439]	[579439]	128	0.0025	300	MCE	300
	CT-ED-Emul1	[9x480]	[579439]	128	0.005	100	MSE	2000
SR	CT-ED-Emul2-3	[[9x480], [911x2222]]	[579439]	128	0.005	100	MSE	2000,300
	SR-AE-Offshore	[5x480]	[5x480]	64	0.0035	300	MCE	600
	SR-AE-Deform	[948x1300]	[948x1300]	64	0.0025	100	MSE	300
	SR-AE-Onshore	[224124]	[224124]	128	0.0025	300	MCE	300
	SR-ED-Emul1	[5x480]	[224124]	128	0.005	100	MSE	2000
	SR-ED-Emul2-3	[[5x480], [948x1300]]	[224124]	128	0.005	100	MSE	2000,300

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